

Protocol Parasitoids of *Philaenus spumarius* – BeXyl Project 2023

Methodology

ABBREVIATIONS: Ps = *Philaenus spumarius*

1) Sentinel eggs for egg parasitoids

Retrieving eggs for field exposition

Eggs are obtained from mass rearings of Ps adults.

First, Spittlebugs are captured in late summer (September) in meadows by sweep net. Ps adults are then released in cages (Bugdorm: 45×45×90 cm) and cylinders (diam. 14 cm, H 40 cm) with (barley) straw as oviposition substrate. Host plants present in cages for rearing are mixed: both herbaceous (*Vicia faba*, *Cichorium intybus*, *Conyza canadensis*, *Avena sativa*) and woody (*Abies* spp., *Corylus avellana*). Straw is placed directly on the soil present in pots.

- If possible, do a quick selection of straw, choosing pieces with sheath leaves around the culms, the best place for oviposition.
- Possibly, best isolate single couples (or 1 female with 2-3 males) in small cages or cylinders around a single pot. It seems the solution that allow to obtain the maximum number of eggs/female.

Rearings are maintained in field climatic conditions (North Italy) under a cover (screenhouse) to limit mortality of Ps adults caused by excess rain/water.

Ps adults may continue to oviposit till late November (North Italy)

Eggs removal

Straw removal is carried out in autumn/winter period, when logistically convenient. It is possible to perform a frequent removal and substitution of straw during oviposition period, but it is time and work demanding.

Once removed, straw can be stored in cold climatic chamber (6-10°C, 16:8 l:d) in plastic containers (19×14×3.5 cm) on a soft net placed on a layer (ca. 2 cm) of humid perlite. Plastic containers have small holes to avoid excess humidity inside. Pure water (ca. 5 mL) is added to perlite approx. every 1-2 weeks or when needed.

Egg counting

Straw is carefully checked first by the naked eye to look for signs of egg masses (e.g., whitish foam), then moved under stereomicroscope (10-20x) to open/uncover egg masses and count the number of eggs. Eggs masses are not separated as much as possible, but the foamy whitish cover is just scraped when needed to count the eggs present. Once counted, straw pieces with counted egg masses on them may be placed in cold climatic chamber in the same condition as described above for the straw, although the egg masses are placed over a filter paper layer with humid perlite below, to maintain a high level of humidity.

Preparation of sentinel eggs

We tested four setups to exposed sentinel eggs in the field:

- 1) Tent: eggs are exposed in plastic tray (19×14×3.5 cm) with moist ground, covered by polycarbonate foil.

- 2) Cylinder – fine mesh: eggs are exposed in pots filled with moist perlite and isolated with cylindrical isolator (h 40 cm, Ø 14 cm) in plastic net (2 cm), covered with a fine net (mesh: 2 mm).
- 3) Cylinder – wide mesh: eggs are exposed in pots filled with moist perlite and isolated in cylindrical isolator (h 40 cm, Ø 14 cm) in plastic net (5 mm)
- 4) Field rearing: As an alternative, adults (mainly females) of the spittlebug can be isolated in a net cage (h 50 cm Ø 45 cm) with plants (*Vicia faba*, *Olea europea*, *Picea abies*) and straw for oviposition. Eggs are then collected as for sentinel eggs.

Different setups are exposed in hidden places in several sites and environments. Eggs (setups 1-3) are placed inside the setup directly in the field.

Different exposure periods are tested: early (September – November); mid (November – January); late (January – February).

Sentinel eggs are collected at the end of each period, and straw is placed in clear plastic containers with filter paper and perlite directly in the field.

Monitoring parasitoid emergence

Upon arrival in lab facilities, collected egg masses are put in cold climate chamber (6 °C, 16:8 L:D). Within one month from collection, they are placed in Petri dishes (Ø 8 cm) and moved to a warm climatic chamber (18–20 °C, 14:10 L:D). Petri are then checked every two days, until the emergence of parasitoids or spittlebug nymphs. Both parasitoids and spittlebug nymphs emerging are counted and immediately removed from Petri.

2) Pipunculidae monitoring

Sampling PS

To evaluate the presence and prevalence of *Verrallia aucta* or other Pipunculidae parasitoids, PS adults are sampled in late summer (August-September) in different sites of north-western Italy, using sweep net. Agroecosystems of interest are meadows, olive groves and vineyards. Immediately after the sampling, PS adults can be stored in alcohol 70% for dissection or in pure alcohol for molecular analyses (PCR).

Detection

Molecular analyses are used to evaluate the presence of *V. aucta* in the sampled PS population. DNA is extracted by single insect and stored in the refrigerator at minus 20 degrees. DNA is used in qPCR to amplify the target gene ITS2, using the specific primers ValITS2 Fw and ValITS2 Rv (Molinatto et al., 2020) to assess the presence and prevalence of *V. aucta* in PS. A subsample can be used to perform both dissection and molecular analysis to validate the results and evaluate, possibly, the presence of other Pipunculidae parasitoids (in case a dipteran larva is present but PCR specific to *V. aucta* is negative).

References

Molinatto G, Demichelis S, Bodino N, et al (2020) Biology and Prevalence in Northern Italy of *Verrallia aucta* (Diptera, Pipunculidae), a Parasitoid of *Philaenus spumarius* (Hemiptera, Aphrophoridae), the Main Vector of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Europe. *Insects* 11:607. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects11090607>